

FOMO26: Foundation Model Challenge for Brain MRI: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

FOMO26: Foundation Model Challenge for Brain MRI

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

FOMO26

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Large-scale self-supervised pretraining offers significant yet underutilised opportunities for advancing brain magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) analysis. Despite recent progress, most state-of-the-art methods continue to rely on fully supervised learning. While strong data augmentation can yield competitive performance with limited annotations, such approaches often struggle under domain shift and degraded clinical image quality, limiting their reliability in real-world settings. Foundation models trained via self-supervised pretraining on large, heterogeneous datasets offer a promising alternative, but their true benefits over supervised models remain insufficiently and inconsistently evaluated.

To address this gap, we present a new edition of FOMO, a MICCAI challenge designed to rigorously assess foundation models for brain MRI using large-scale, diverse datasets and comprehensive evaluation, with a strong emphasis on real-world clinical routine data and out-of-domain settings. A central contribution of this challenge is a substantially expanded pretraining dataset comprising 318,877 brain MRI scans from 82,678 MRI sessions and 59,969 subjects, aggregated from 920 publicly available sources, providing a realistic substrate for large-scale self-supervised representation learning.

This year's challenge comprises seven downstream tasks, spanning image-level classification, voxel-wise segmentation, regression, and representation quality assessment. The first three tasks continue benchmarks from the previous edition, enabling longitudinal comparison, while four new tasks substantially broaden the clinical and methodological scope. For all tasks, fine-tuning is explicitly limited to few-shot regimes. Evaluation is performed on hidden, large-scale, multi-institutional out-of-domain clinical datasets, comprising several hundred to several thousand cases per task, ensuring that performance reflects genuine generalization rather than task-specific overfitting.

To encourage methodological transparency and broad participation, each task is offered under two

complementary tracks: a Method track, restricting participants to challenge-provided data only, and an Open track, permitting the use of external or private data. This dual-track design enables fair comparison of representation learning strategies while also allowing exploration of scaling effects, architectural choices, and data curation strategies beyond the challenge data alone.

By evaluating pretrained models across a diverse set of clinically grounded downstream tasks, the challenge is designed to move beyond task-specific or noise-driven improvements and to enable a more reliable assessment of whether self-supervised pretraining yields consistent and generalizable advantages over fully supervised approaches. Ultimately, FOMO26 aims to advance the development of clinically reliable foundation models for brain MRI, with attention to robustness, fairness, and real-world applicability.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Foundation models, self-supervised learning, out-of-domain generalization, few-shot learning, brain MRI, clinical data

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge extends last year's edition by substantially increasing both the scale of pretraining data and the breadth of downstream evaluation. The publicly provided pretraining dataset has expanded from approximately 60k to over 300k 3D MRI scans, making it the largest openly available pretraining resource for brain MRI to date and further lowering the barrier to entry for large-scale self-supervised learning.

In addition, the challenge includes a larger and more diverse set of downstream tasks, all evaluated under few-shot learning and domain shift settings, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of the generality and robustness of learned representations. The involvement of additional institutions further increases data heterogeneity and strengthens the evaluation of cross-site generalization.

Importantly, the first three tasks retain an identical setup from last year, providing a direct benchmark to track algorithm performance between the two editions.

Together, these aspects make the challenge a unique and rigorous benchmark for measuring progress in brain MRI foundation models beyond single-task or single-domain evaluations.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The primary aim of this extended edition of the challenge is to assess whether brain MRI foundation models can learn robust representations across a broader range of tasks, and whether they provide consistent advantages over supervised, task-specific approaches. By including a larger and more diverse set of downstream tasks, the challenge aims to better distinguish genuine improvements in representation learning from task-specific

adaptations. Evaluation focuses on few-shot learning and robustness to domain shifts, rather than immediate clinical deployment. While the downstream tasks are clinically motivated, substantial additional validation and regulatory approval would be required before any clinical application.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

This challenge is not part of a workshop.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

The challenge results will be combined with talks from invited speakers on foundation models for medical imaging as well as presentations from top-performing participating teams. The number of teams presenting will be decided based on the total number of participants and the available time.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect the challenge to attract the interest of a substantial number of submissions. For FOMO25, the participation statistics were:

- * 122 users signed up from 25 different countries.
- * 18 teams with 30 users in total submitted at least one container, 17 teams submitted to all three tasks.
- * 20 valid submissions (each submission contained 3 containers) in total, with three teams submitting to both tracks.

Given the popularity of the subject area, we expect the challenge this year to increase in popularity and, at a minimum, match FOMO25. We are very focused on lowering the technical bar for participating in this challenge. For this reason, we will:

- * Release a public GitHub repo with example code that performs both pretraining and finetuning using an MAE-pretext task.
- * Release pretrained checkpoints for this baseline model, allowing participants with access to smaller compute environments to investigate continual-pretraining and advanced finetuning techniques.
- * Release code and data that allow users to start pretraining and finetuning with no additional preprocessing.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

The aim is a publication in a journal such as Nature Methods, Medical Image Analysis, npj Digital Medicine, Nature Communications, or TMI. Expected journal submission Q4 2026 - Q1 2027.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

No

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Participants are required to train models using their own compute environment. The minimum practical requirement for participation is estimated to be one compute node with at least one GPU with 40 GB of VRAM. To decrease the participation barrier, we are further releasing Pretrained checkpoints for a simple baseline model, allowing participants with access to smaller compute environments to investigate continual pretraining and advanced finetuning techniques.

TASK 1: Infarct Classification

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The focus of this task is to evaluate pretrained models on the task of few-shot image-level infarct classification. Finetuning and evaluation datasets consist of real-world, clinical data from two different distributions.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

few-shot classification, robustness, clinical data

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Stefano Cerri* [1, 2, 3]

Asbjørn Munk* [1, 2]

Jakob Ambsdorf [1, 2]

Sebastian Nørgaard Llambias [1, 2]

Llucia Coll [4]

Alice Schiavone [1]

Leila Khaertdinova [1]

Julia Machnio [1, 2]

Pablo Rocamora García [1, 2]

Zahra Sobhaninia [1, 2]

Simon Winther Albertsen [1]

Said Djafar Said [1]

Christian Hedeager Krag [5]

Vardan Nersesjan [3, 6]

Mostafa Mehdipour Ghazi [1, 2]

Juan Eugenio Iglesias [7, 8]

Mikael Ploug Boesen [5, 9]

Espen Jimenez Solem [9]

Bulat Ibragimov [1]

Peirong Liu [10]

Melanie Benjamin Ganz [1, 4]

Risheng Xu [10]

Michael Eriksen Benros [3, 11]

Mads Nielsen [1, 2]

* Lead Organizer

[1] Department of Computer Science, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

[2] Pioneer Centre For AI, Denmark

[3] Copenhagen Research Centre for Biological and Precision Psychiatry, Mental Health Centre Copenhagen, Copenhagen University Hospital, Denmark

[4] Neurobiology Research Unit, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Denmark

[5] Radiological AI Testcenter, Denmark

[6] Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Denmark

[7] Athinoula A. Martinos Center for Biomedical Imaging, Massachusetts General Hospital and Harvard Medical School, USA

[8] Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence Laboratory, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA

[9] Copenhagen University Hospital, Bispebjerg & Frederiksberg Hospital, Denmark

[10] Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, USA

[11] Department of Clinical Medicine, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Stefano Cerri (stce@di.ku.dk)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Vardan Nersesjan and Christian Krag provided image-level infarct annotations and inputs on inclusion and exclusion criteria and clinical relevance of the task.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

This is a repeated event with a fixed conference submission deadline. Building on the outcomes and feedback from last year's challenge, this year's edition extends the original three tasks with additional new tasks, while retaining the core challenge structure. We expect to also run the challenge for MICCAI 2027 and onwards. The pretraining data will remain available for use after the submission deadline, which we expect to continue to be a significant contribution to the development of foundation models for brain MRI. Further, we are currently exploring technical solutions for keeping the leaderboard open after the challenge has concluded; however, this remains a significant technical challenge due to the information security requirements for the compute platform storing the evaluation data.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Synapse.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The challenge website is accessible through <https://fomo26.github.io>. The Synapse link will be <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn72120565/wiki/637260>, which will be linked to from the main challenge website

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed for curating pretraining data. No user interaction is allowed for annotating additional data for finetuning or for manually correcting outputs at the image or voxel level. Users may exclude or filter samples from the finetuning dataset, but may not add new data, annotations, or corrections.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

For all tasks, the challenge will have two tracks: 1. No additional data allowed: Challenge participants can only use data provided in the challenge for their submissions. 2. Any data allowed: Challenge participants can use any data, including private data, for their submissions. This track includes submissions using any form of segmentation maps obtained through manual labor or disease diagnosis information during pretraining. All data used must be specified and properly cited.

The organizers provide a dataset that can be used for pretraining models in the challenge, consisting of 318,877 brain Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) scans from 82,678 MRI sessions and 59,969 subjects, aggregated from 920 publicly available sources [1].

Participants must use only the provided finetune data if they choose to finetune; using no finetuning data is also permitted.

[1] Munk*, A., Cerri*, S., Ambsdorf, J., Machnio, J., Llambias, S. N., Nersesjan, V., ... & Nielsen, M. (2025). A large-scale heterogeneous 3D magnetic resonance brain imaging dataset for self-supervised learning. arXiv preprint arXiv:2506.14432.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Due to the large number of members in the institutes of the organizers, these are divided into two groups: 1. Participants who have active working relations with any of the organizers are not allowed to participate and will not be listed on the leaderboard. 2. Other members of the institutes may participate, but are not eligible for awards and listed with a clearly visible disclaimer in leaderboard.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge will seek to raise funding for prize money in the order of magnitude of \$2000 in total for, but not limited to, the top three teams, defined as the teams with the best ranking on each track leaderboard.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The full leaderboards for the test data will be announced as soon as possible after the submission deadline. Top participants will be invited to present their methods during an oral presentation.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participating teams that have made substantial submissions (e.g., excludes trivial approaches such as setting all outputs to zero, random guessing, or simply using provided baselines) to all the tasks will be invited to participate in the following publication. Each team can have at most five authors on the publication. We will consider exemptions on a case-by-case basis.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container on the Synapse platform. Submission instructions will be available at <https://fomo26.github.io>, including example code and example Docker containers. The submission is subject to a runtime limit of 120 seconds per case on a compute node with an 80GB VRAM H100 GPU and 32 CPUs.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be able to evaluate their algorithms on a held-out validation set before the final submission. The validation dataset will be available for more than one month, and participants will be allowed to evaluate their algorithms three times at maximum. This will give participants clear signals on the performance of their models, but discourage over-optimization on the validation split.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

1. April: Challenge registration opens, including access to pretraining dataset and finetuning data. Release public GitHub repo with example code that performs both pretraining and finetuning using an MAE-pretext task and a U-Net backbone.

15. May: Access to sanity-check pipeline on Synapse opens (technical evaluation, which confirms that the container is correctly configured).

15. June: Validation leaderboard opens, and final submission pipeline opens.

21. August: Challenge submission deadline.

Results will be released during MICCAI 2026 (4 October or 8 October).

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Each dataset included in the pretraining and finetuning datasets was acquired under approval from the relevant legal and ethics boards by the original data providers. Validation and test datasets were approved by the Danish Patient Safety (Styrelsen for Patientsikkerhed, approval #31-1521-257) and the Danish Data Protection Agency (Datatilsynet, approval #P-2020-320).

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

Pretraining data may be used in accordance with the usage terms described in the following article [1] and data repository [2]. FOMO300K is distributed as a collection released under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0) license [3]. Each individual dataset within the collection retains its original license. Some datasets are additionally subject to Data Use Agreements (DUAs), which are reported in the usage term when requesting access to the data [2]. Users must comply with the applicable license terms and any associated DUAs. Finetuning data for Tasks 1 and 2 is restricted exclusively to use within the scope of this challenge and cannot be used for any purpose beyond submitting entries for the competition. Tasks 3, 4, and 5 datasets follow the usage terms of the provided data owner. Validation and test data will remain private and will not be distributed to participants. [1] Cerri*, S., Munk*, A., Llambias, S. N., Ambsdorf, J., Machnio, J., Nersesjan, V., ... & Nielsen, M. (2026). A large-scale heterogeneous 3D magnetic resonance brain imaging dataset for self-supervised learning. arXiv preprint arXiv:2506.14432. [2] <https://huggingface.co/datasets/FOMO-MRI/FOMO300K> [3] <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/deed.en>

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

All evaluation code will be made public. Code is based on the Yucca framework [1], which is publicly available on PyPi and closely mimics the way nnUnet [2] performs evaluation. The evaluation script can be used on any machine that supports PyTorch >2.0.0.

[1] Llambias, S.N., Machnio, J., Munk, A., Ambsdorf, J., Nielsen, M., Ghazi, M.M.: Yucca: A deep learning framework for medical image analysis. arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.19888 (2024), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.19888>

[2] Isensee, F., Jaeger, P.F., Kohl, S.A.A., Petersen, J., Maier-Hein, K.: nnu-net: a self-configuring method for deep learning-based biomedical image segmentation. Nature Methods 18, 203 – 211 (2020), <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41592-020-01008-z>

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Submissions and code of participating teams will not be made public; participants are free to publicize their submissions at their own discretion.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Mads Nielsen owns shares of Cerebriu, who is the co-organizer of this challenge.

Only Stefano Cerri, Sebastian Llambias, Asbjørn Munk, Vardan Nersesjan, and Christian Hedager Krag have had access to the test labels. Access to this has been in the following three contexts:

- * Producing the labels.
- * Writing evaluation code.
- * Executing evaluation of submissions.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization

- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Few-shot Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

18-year-old or older patients with possible brain infarct(s).

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Subjects who underwent an MRI scan and were subsequently diagnosed with infarcts and a control group in 2019 in multiple hospitals in Denmark (evaluation data) and India (finetuning data).

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI scans of the brain, always including T2 FLAIR, DWI (ADC and b-value 1000), and either T2* or SWI images, are used for the Finetuning, Validation, and Test datasets.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pretrain: None. Finetune: binary mask of infarct. Validation and Testing: None.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Pretrain: age, gender, MRI metadata, and patients' group. Finetune, Validation, and Testing: None.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary,

differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain MRI scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Image-based classification of patients with brain infarcts, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Binary classification of the presence or absence of infarcts on MRI scans, AUROC, Robustness, Few-shot Generalization

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Pretrain dataset: multiple scanners from different vendors. Finetune dataset: multiple scanners from GE and Siemens. Validation and Test datasets: multiple scanners from GE, Siemens, and Philips.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The acquisition protocols are highly heterogeneous and vary across hospitals, as scans were acquired during real-world routine clinical practice. Detailed information about the acquisition parameters for each scan will be made available as supplementary material in the challenge meta-analysis manuscript.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Pretrain provided by the organizers: a highly heterogeneous dataset of brain MRI scans, aggregated from 920 sources from [1].

Finetune dataset: Bodyscan Diagnostics, Indore, India. The dataset contains data from multiple hospitals related to Bodyscan Diagnostics and has been provided by the Copenhagen-based startup Cerebriu.

Validation and test datasets: Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen; Bispebjerg & Frederiksberg Hospital, Copenhagen; Nordsjællands Hospital, Hillerød; Bornholms Hospital, Rønne; Amager & Hvidovre Hospital, Copenhagen; Herlev & Gentofte Hospital, Copenhagen; Region Sjællands Sygehusvæsen. All hospitals are located in The Capital Region of

Denmark and part of Region Sjælland.

The datasets of finetuning and validation are taken from different source distributions in order to gauge the generalization abilities of the pretrained models under domain shift, while harmonizing the MRI sequence types and labeling protocols.

[1] Munk*, A., Cerri*, S., Ambsdorf, J., Machnio, J., Llambias, S. N., Nersesjan, V., ... & Nielsen, M. (2025). A large-scale heterogeneous 3D magnetic resonance brain imaging dataset for self-supervised learning. arXiv preprint arXiv:2506.14432

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Healthcare professionals responsible for performing MRI scans on patients with possible brain-related conditions during regular clinical workflows.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific MRI visit. For Finetuning, Validation, and Test datasets, information always includes T2-FLAIR and DWI (ADC and b-value 1000), and either T2* or SWI MRI scans, and image-level label indicating the presence or absence of infarct(s). Each finetuning case belonging to the positive class has an additional binary segmentation mask delineating the infarct. These masks are provided only for the finetuning dataset, and may be used to explore alternative finetune strategies.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Pretraining cases from the organizers: 82,678. Finetune cases: 21. Validation cases: 80. Test cases: 320.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All data is already annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

* Pretraining dataset is the largest publicly available pretraining dataset for brain MRI.

* For all tasks, the finetuning datasets are kept small to condition the performance on the quality of the pretraining and to evaluate the model's few-shot performance under domain shifts.

* For all tasks, the validation datasets are kept small to only gauge the performance of the methods under

distribution shift.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

13 finetuning cases are from the positive class (presence of infarcts), and 8 are from the negative class (absence of infarcts). The validation and test cases have equal class distribution.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Validation and test datasets remain unseen to participants, but were previously used in last year's challenge.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Pretraining dataset: None. Finetuning, validation, and test datasets: Positive examples were selected based on ICD-10 code I63 (Cerebral infarction), and negative examples were selected based on the absence of ICD-10 codes I63 and I64 (Stroke, not specified as haemorrhage or infarction). All cases were visually inspected by two expert annotators, with radiology reports consulted in cases of uncertainty, to provide image-level annotations of the presence or absence of infarcts. Cases with disagreements between the two annotators were excluded.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Image-level classification of infarcts (presence (positive class) or absence (negative class)) was performed primarily using DWI scans. In cases where potential infarct areas on DWI were unclear, FLAIR, T2*, and/or SWI scans were utilized to confirm or rule out the presence of acute or subacute infarcts.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Two expert annotators were used, with expertise in Radiology and Neurology, respectively. Both annotators are medical doctors and have completed at least the 1st year of residency in their respective fields. One annotator has obtained a PhD in Neurology, and another annotator has obtained a PhD in Radiology.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Disagreements among raters were excluded.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Finetune, validation, and test datasets are minimally processed to allow users to define and control data processing pipelines. Each individual scan is RAS-oriented, skull-stripped using SynthSeg, and each sequence is affinely coregistered using `mri_coreg` from FreeSurfer to the highest resolution scan in the same MRI visit, or, when manual delineations are available, to the reference scan used for delineation. For scans in the pretraining dataset provided by the organizers, see [1]

[1] Munk*, A., Cerri*, S., Ambsdorf, J., Machnio, J., Llambias, S. N., Nersesjan, V., ... & Nielsen, M. (2025). A large-scale heterogeneous 3D magnetic resonance brain imaging dataset for self-supervised learning. arXiv preprint arXiv:2506.14432.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Labels for the Validation and Test datasets are derived from the ICD-10 code I63 and visually confirmed, introducing potential subjectivity and error.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Multi-class counting metrics: N/A

Per-class counting metric: N/A

Multi-threshold metrics: AUROC (Area Under the Receiver Operator Curve (ROC))

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics have been chosen by following the recommendations set forth in Metrics Reloaded [1]. The following contains the problem-specific answers for Image-level classification:

Question: Which cutoff method on predicted class scores fits your problem more?

Answer: No decision rule applied

Justification: This challenge seeks to make methodological comparisons, with no concrete clinical use-case in mind.

Question: Are predicted class probabilities available in your research?

Answer: Yes

Question: Do the provided class prevalences reflect the population of interest in your research?

Answer: No

Question: Is calibration assessment requested in your research?

Answer: No

We follow the recommendation of not including any per-class counting metrics and to evaluate models using AUROC.

[1] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nature methods, 21(2):195–212, 2024.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

For each task, all test cases are assigned a uniform weight, and each metric is averaged over all cases in the test set. The ranking procedure will follow those used in previous challenges like TIGER and DECATHLON.

Per-task leaderboard:

For each task, a per-task summary statistic is computed as the average of the ranks across metrics (or the rank itself if the task has only one metric). Submissions are then ranked based on this summary statistic.

Unified leaderboard:

The overall rank is computed as a weighted average of per-task ranks: 10% for each of the five image-level tasks (Task 1, Task 3, Task 5, Task 6, and Task 7) and 25% for each of the voxel-level tasks (Task 2 and Task 4). For tasks not included in a submission, the worst possible rank for that task is used. Weighting ensures that no task type dominates the leaderboard, preventing bias toward specific pretraining strategies, as observed in the first edition of the challenge.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For missing metric values for test cases, submissions are evaluated by setting the score to the worst possible value. For AUROC, is the wrong class prediction with 100% certainty.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

A leaderboard provides a concise summary of results, offering a clear comparison across tasks, and is both simple to implement and to interpret.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Model performance is primarily evaluated using rank-based comparisons across metrics and tasks.

Ranking stability is quantified via bootstrap resampling of test subjects with replacement, recomputing rankings to obtain rank distributions (i.e., sensitivity to test set composition), following the SSL3D challenge [2].

Statistical significance of performance differences between algorithms is assessed using subject-wise, non-parametric permutation testing of relative ranks within the test set. This approach is chosen because it does not rely on distributional assumptions, accounts for the paired nature of the data at the subject level, and is robust to non-normal and bounded performance metrics. Pairwise p-values are computed to assess differences between ranked approaches and are summarized in upper triangular matrices, which are used to identify groups of methods with statistically indistinguishable performance (tiers). The overall methodology follows the evaluation framework established by the BraTS challenge series [1].

[1] S. Bakas et al., Identifying the Best Machine Learning Algorithms for Brain Tumor Segmentation, Progression Assessment, and Overall Survival Prediction in the BRATS Challenge, arXiv:1811.02629 [cs, stat], Apr. 2019, Accessed: Dec. 10, 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1811.02629>

[2] Ulrich, C., et al. Self-Supervised Learning for 3D Medical Imaging (SSL3D) Challenge. Zenodo, 24 Mar. 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15119044>.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Precision of performance estimates for each algorithm is assessed using aggregated performance metrics computed over the test set. Uncertainty is summarized using confidence intervals of the mean performance, estimated via non-parametric bootstrap resampling across test cases.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Variability of each algorithm's performance across test cases is quantified using either standard deviation or interquartile range, depending on the presence of outliers in the data. All reported summaries are aggregated over groups of five or more cases to comply with data protection and re-identification rules.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Variability of algorithm rankings is assessed using a bootstrap approach based on [1, 2] of ranks across metrics and tasks. Across bootstrap samples, the sensitivity of ranks for each algorithm is examined to quantify ranking stability. This approach follows the MICCAI 2025 SSL3D challenges approach as described in [3].

[1] Maier-Hein, L., Eisenmann, M., Reinke, A. et al. "Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care" Nature Communications 9, 5217 (2018)

[2] Wiesenfarth, Manuel, et al. "Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results." Scientific reports 11.1 (2021): 2369.

[3] Ulrich, C., et al. Self-Supervised Learning for 3D Medical Imaging (SSL3D) Challenge. Zenodo, 24 Mar. 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15119044>.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

The ranks of teams will be complemented with statistical analysis to assess the significance of performance differences. For each task, per-task p-values are computed via permutation testing: team predictions are randomly swapped, all metrics are recomputed, and teams are ranked per metric. If a task has multiple metrics, ranks are averaged to obtain an aggregated rank. This procedure is repeated for a large number of permutations (100,000) to estimate the probability that observed rank differences could occur by chance.

Global p-values are then aggregated across tasks to provide an overall assessment of performance. Teams are sorted by mean rank and grouped into tiers based on pairwise global p-values. This framework applies to all tasks and metrics.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Missing or invalid outputs for a given test case are handled by assigning the worst possible performance for the corresponding metric. This ensures that all methods are included in the ranking while penalizing incomplete submissions. No imputation of performance metrics will be performed.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

All analyses will be performed in Python using common libraries like NumPy, SciPy, and pandas. Evaluation metrics are implemented in custom Python scripts. The evaluation code and metric implementations will be publicly available and version-controlled.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Further analyses will seek to investigate the correlation between performance and:

- * Different pretraining methodologies, grouping by similar methodological categories (e.g., reconstruction vs. self-distillation vs. contrastive learning, etc.)
- * Using private data, specifically on the impact of pretraining dataset size.
- * Different backbones.
- * Model sizes and capacities, measured in FLOPS and total number of parameters.

The analysis is not limited to the above, and may include the relationship between performance and other attributes of the submissions.

TASK 2: Meningioma Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

This task evaluates pretrained models on the task of few-shot meningioma segmentation. Finetuning and evaluation datasets consist of real-world, clinical data from two different distributions.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

few-shot segmentation, robustness, clinical data

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

See Task 1.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Asbjørn Munk (asmu@di.ku.dk)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Vardan Nersesjan and Christian Krag provided manual meningioma segmentations and inputs on inclusion and exclusion criteria and clinical relevance.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

See Task 1.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

See Task 1.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

See Task 1.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

See Task 1.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

See Task 1.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

See Task 1.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

See Task 1.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

See Task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)

- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

See Task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

See Task 1.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

See Task 1.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

See Task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

See Task 1.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)

- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

See Task 1.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

See Task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

See Task 1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

See Task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Few-shot Segmentation**Cohorts**

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

18-year-old or older preoperative meningioma patients.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Subjects who underwent an MRI diagnosed with preoperative meningioma in 2019 in multiple hospitals in Denmark (evaluation data) and India (finetuning data).

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI scans of the brain, always including T2 FLAIR, DWI (b-value 1000), and either T2* or SWI images, are used for the Finetuning, Validation, and Test datasets.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pretrain: None. Finetune: binary mask of meningiomas. Validation and Testing: None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Pretrain: see Task 1. Finetune, Validation, and Testing: None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain MRI scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Patients with brain meningiomas scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Binary segmentation of brain meningiomas on MRI scans, Dice, Normalized Surface Distance, Robustness, Few-shot Generalization

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Pretrain dataset: same as Task 1. Finetune dataset: multiple scanners from GE, Siemens, and Philips. Validation and Test datasets: multiple scanners from GE, Siemens, and Philips.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

See Task 1.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

See Task 1.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Healthcare professionals responsible for performing MRI scans on patients with possible brain-related conditions during regular clinical workflows.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific MRI visit. For finetuning, Validation, and Test datasets, information always includes T2-FLAIR and DWI (b-value 1000), and either T2* or SWI MRI scans, and a binary segmentation mask delineating the meningiomas.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Pretraining cases: same as Task 1. Finetune cases: 23. Validation cases: 25. Test cases: 107.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All data is already annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

See Task 1.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Not applicable.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Validation and test datasets remain unseen to participants, but were previously used in last year's challenge

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Manual image annotation of the meningiomas was performed. For the finetuning, validation, and test datasets, delineations were carried out by two annotators, each annotating approximately half of the scans.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The manual delineation protocol follows the BraTS Meningioma Segmentation Challenge [1], with the only difference being that we provide binary masks instead of multi-label masks.

[1] LaBella et al., "A multi-institutional meningioma MRI dataset for automated multi-sequence image segmentation," *Scientific Data*, 11:496, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03350-9>.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See Task 1.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No multiple annotations are available.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See Task 1. Each individual scan has been defaced using the midface command from FreeSurfer (version 7.4.1) instead of skull-stripped using SynthSeg to account for meningiomas appearing in proximity to the skull.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Manual delineations by expert annotators may contain errors due to subjective bias. No inter-annotator variability has been estimated.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Overlap-based metric: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

Boundary-based metric: Normal Surface Distance (NSD)

Volume metric: N/A

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics have been chosen by following the recommendations set forth in Metrics Reloaded [1]. The following contains the problem-specific answers for semantic segmentation:

Question: Does your data feature consistently small structures relative to pixel size?

Answer: No

Question: Is there exclusive interest in structure centers in your research?

Answer: No

Question: According to the this information, do class confusions, i.e., over- vs. undersegmentation, have equal or unequal weight in your study?

Answer: Equal handling

Question: Are there overlapping or touching target structures in your data?

Answer: No

Question: Is there particular importance of structure boundaries in your research?

Answer: Yes

Question: Is compensation for annotation imprecisions requested in your research?

Answer: Yes

We follow the recommendation of using the following metrics:

Overlap-based metric: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

Boundary-based metric: Normal Surface Distance (NSD)

We have decided not to use any volume metric since this challenge seeks to make methodological comparisons, with no concrete clinical use case in mind.

[1] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nature methods, 21(2):195–212, 2024.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

See Task 1.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For missing metric values for test cases, submissions are evaluated by setting the score to the worst possible value. For DSC and NSD, the worst possible value is 0.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

See Task 1.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

See Task 1.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

See Task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

See Task 1.

TASK 3: Brain Age Estimation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

This task evaluates pretrained models on a regression problem, using real-world clinical data from two different distributions for finetuning and evaluation.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

regression, robustness, clinical data

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

See Task 1.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Stefano Cerri (stce@di.ku.dk)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Vardan Nersesjan and Christian Krag provided inputs on inclusion and exclusion criteria and clinical relevance of the task.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

See Task 1.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

See Task 1.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

See Task 1.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

See Task 1.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

See Task 1.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

See Task 1.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

See Task 1.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

See Task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)

- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

See Task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

See Task 1.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

See Task 1.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

See Task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

See Task 1.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)

- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

See Task 1.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

See Task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

See Task 1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

See Task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Regression

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients 18 years or older with no underlying brain conditions, defined as patients with no neurological conditions and not on brain-related medication.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Subjects who underwent an MRI with no underlying brain conditions in 2019 in multiple hospitals in Denmark (evaluation data) and Boston (finetuning data).

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI scans of the brain, always including T1w and T2w images for Finetuning, Validation, and Test datasets.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pretrain, Finetune, Validation, and Testing: None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Pretrain: see Task 1. Finetune: Age. Validation and Testing: None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain MRI scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Age of patients with no underlying brain conditions, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accurate prediction of the age of the patient based on MRI scans, Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Pretrain dataset: same as Task 1. Finetune dataset: multiple scanners from GE, Siemens, and Philips. Validation and Test datasets: multiple scanners from GE, Siemens, and Philips.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

See Task 1.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Finetune dataset: Massachusetts General Hospital, a subset from MGH Wild [1]. For other datasets, see Task 1.

[1] Juan E. Iglesias et al. ,SynthSR: A public AI tool to turn heterogeneous clinical brain scans into high-resolution T1-weighted images for 3D morphometry. Sci.Adv.9, eadd3607(2023). DOI:10.1126/sciadv.add3607.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Healthcare professionals responsible for performing MRI scans on patients with possible brain-related conditions during regular clinical workflows.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific MRI visit. For Finetuning, Validation, and Test datasets, information always includes T1w and T2w MRI scans, and age.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Pretraining cases: same as Task 1. Finetune cases: 200. Validation Cases: 200. Test cases: 800.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All data is already annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

See Task 1.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Not applicable.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Validation and test datasets remain unseen to participants, but were previously used in last year's challenge

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For each case in the Finetune, Validation, and Test datasets, age (in years) at the time of the MRI visit is provided.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Not applicable.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not applicable.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No multiple annotations are available.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See Task 1.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Although we exclude patients with neurological conditions and those on brain-related medication, non-brain conditions may still indirectly affect brain age estimation, introducing potential errors and biases.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Metric 1: Absolute Error (AE)

Metric 2: Correlation Coefficient

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Since Metrics Reloaded [1] does not incorporate regression recommendations, we cannot follow the same structured approach as in Tasks 1 and 2. Using AE and the correlation coefficient provides a complementary evaluation: AE measures prediction accuracy while being intuitive and interpretable, while the correlation coefficient assesses the alignment of predictions while penalizing systematic biases.

[1] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nature methods, 21(2):195–212, 2024.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

See Task 1.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For the Absolute Error: Submissions are evaluated by setting the absolute error to the worst possible value for the test, defined as the value 100.

For correlation coefficient: missing test case predictions are set to -100, and this value is used to calculate the correlation coefficient.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

See Task 1.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

See Task 1.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

See Task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

See Task 1.

TASK 4: Trigeminal Neuralgia Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The focus of this task is to evaluate pretrained models on the task of trigeminal neuralgia (TN) segmentation, including nerve and vessel segmentations. Finetuning and evaluation datasets consist of real-world, clinical data from two different distributions.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

few-shot segmentation, clinical data

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

See Task 1.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Peirong Liu (peirong@jhu.edu)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes (Risheng Xu): Providing manual TN annotations and clinical inputs

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

See Task 1.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

See Task 1.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

See Task 1.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

See Task 1.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

See Task 1.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

See Task 1.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

See Task 1.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

See Task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)

- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

See Task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

See Task 1. Code will run on NVIDIA RTX PRO 6000 Blackwell GPU with 32 CPUs or NVIDIA H200 with 32 CPUs

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

See Task 1.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

See Task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Pretraining data: See Task 1.

Finetuning data: Subset of OpenNeuro dataset in [1]

Validation and Test data:

Study Number: CIR00126070 For: IRB00338945

Study Name: Outcomes of patients with trigeminal neuralgia

[1] Elena Filimonova, Anton Pashkov, Azniv Martirosyan, Vladimir Kurilov, Galina Moysak, and Jamil Rzaev (2025). A large-scale dataset of pre- and post-surgical MRI data in patients with chronic trigeminal neuralgia. OpenNeuro. [Dataset] doi: doi:10.18112/openneuro.ds005713.v2.0.2

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

See Task 1. For finetuning this specific task, we use a CC0-licensed subset of the OpenNeuro TN dataset [1]. [1] Elena Filimonova, Anton Pashkov, Azniv Martirosyan, Vladimir Kurilov, Galina Moysak, and Jamil Rzaev (2025). A large-scale dataset of pre- and post-surgical MRI data in patients with chronic trigeminal neuralgia. OpenNeuro. [Dataset] doi: doi:10.18112/openneuro.ds005713.v2.0.2

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

See Task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

See Task 1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Peirong Liu and Risheng Xu have access to the validation and test labels for this specific task in the same setting as mentioned in Task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education

- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Few-shot Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients 18 years or older with diagnosed primary trigeminal neuralgia.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Finetuning data: T1w MRI from 40 TN patients selected from the OpenNeuro TN dataset [1]. Validation and Testing data: private Johns Hopkins University cohort of 200 TN patients.

[1] Elena Filimonova, Anton Pashkov, Azniv Martirosyan, Vladimir Kurilov, Galina Moysak, and Jamil Rzaev (2025). A large-scale dataset of pre- and post-surgical MRI data in patients with chronic trigeminal neuralgia. OpenNeuro. [Dataset] doi: doi:10.18112/openneuro.ds005713.v2.0.2

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI scans of the brain, always including T1w images for finetuning, Validation, and Test datasets.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pretrain: None. Finetune: segmentation mask of nerve and vessels. Validation and Testing: None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Pretrain: see Task 1. Finetune: None. Validation and Testing: None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain MRI scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Patients with TN, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Multiclass segmentation of nerve and vessels on MRI scans from TN patients, Dice, Normalized Surface Distance, Robustness, Few-shot Generalization

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Pretrain dataset: same as Task 1. For the Finetune dataset, see [1]. For the Validation and Test dataset, see [2,3].

[1] Elena Filimonova, Anton Pashkov, Azniv Martirosyan, Vladimir Kurilov, Galina Moysak, and Jamil Rzaev (2025). A large-scale dataset of pre- and post-surgical MRI data in patients with chronic trigeminal neuralgia. OpenNeuro. [Dataset] doi: doi:10.18112/openneuro.ds005713.v2.0.2

[2] Xie ME, Halbert-Elliott K, Nair SK, et al. Application of Sequential Thresholding-Based Automated Reconstruction of the Trigeminal Nerve in Trigeminal Neuralgia. *World Neurosurg.* 2024;181:e567-e577. doi:10.1016/j.wneu.2023.10.095

[3] Halbert-Elliott, K. M., Xie, M. E., Dong, B., Das, O., Wang, X., Jackson, C. M., Lim, M., Huang, J., Yedavalli, V. S., Bettgowda, C., & Xu, R. (2025). Deep learning-based segmentation of the trigeminal nerve and surrounding vasculature in trigeminal neuralgia. *Journal of neurosurgery*, 143(1), 83–91. <https://doi.org/10.3171/2024.10.JNS241060>

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

See Task 1.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Pretrain dataset: same as Task 1. For the Finetune dataset, see [1]. For the Validation and Test dataset, see [2,3].

[1] Elena Filimonova, Anton Pashkov, Azniv Martirosyan, Vladimir Kurilov, Galina Moysak, and Jamil Rzaev (2025). A large-scale dataset of pre- and post-surgical MRI data in patients with chronic trigeminal neuralgia. OpenNeuro. [Dataset] doi: doi:10.18112/openneuro.ds005713.v2.0.2

[2] Xie ME, Halbert-Elliott K, Nair SK, et al. Application of Sequential Thresholding-Based Automated Reconstruction of the Trigeminal Nerve in Trigeminal Neuralgia. *World Neurosurg.* 2024;181:e567-e577. doi:10.1016/j.wneu.2023.10.095

[3] Halbert-Elliott, K. M., Xie, M. E., Dong, B., Das, O., Wang, X., Jackson, C. M., Lim, M., Huang, J., Yedavalli, V. S., Bettgowda, C., & Xu, R. (2025). Deep learning-based segmentation of the trigeminal nerve and surrounding vasculature in trigeminal neuralgia. *Journal of neurosurgery*, 143(1), 83–91. <https://doi.org/10.3171/2024.10.JNS241060>

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Healthcare professionals responsible for performing MRI scans on patients with possible brain-related conditions during regular clinical workflows.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific MRI visit. For finetuning, Validation, and Test datasets, information always includes T1w MRI scans and a segmentation mask delineating nerves and vessels.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Pretraining cases: same as Task 1. Finetune cases: 40. Validation cases: 40. Test cases: 160.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

We plan to segment all cases that went through MVD (surgery type) in OpenNeuro TN (for finetune task) manually, which are 40 cases. For the validation and test datasets, all the manual segmentations are ready. The segmentation of the finetune dataset will follow the same labeling protocol as the validation and test datasets.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

See Task 1.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Not applicable.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Validation and test datasets remain unseen to participants.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Manual image annotation of the nerves and vessels was performed for both the Finetune dataset and the Validation and Test datasets.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The manual segmentation protocol follows [1,2] for the finetune, validation, and test datasets.

[1] Xie ME, Halbert-Elliott K, Nair SK, et al. Application of Sequential Thresholding-Based Automated Reconstruction of the Trigeminal Nerve in Trigeminal Neuralgia. *World Neurosurg.* 2024;181:e567-e577. doi:10.1016/j.wneu.2023.10.095

[2] Halbert-Elliott, K. M., Xie, M. E., Dong, B., Das, O., Wang, X., Jackson, C. M., Lim, M., Huang, J., Yedavalli, V. S., Bettgowda, C., & Xu, R. (2025). Deep learning-based segmentation of the trigeminal nerve and surrounding vasculature in trigeminal neuralgia. *Journal of neurosurgery*, 143(1), 83–91. <https://doi.org/10.3171/2024.10.JNS241060>

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Four annotators were used with expertise in Radiology and Neurological Surgery. Two annotators are medical students, supervised by one MD student at Johns Hopkins and one neurosurgeon with an MD and, PhD.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No multiple annotations are available.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See Task 1.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Manual delineations by expert annotators may contain errors due to subjective bias. No inter-annotator variability has been estimated.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Overlap-based metric: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

Boundary-based metric: Normal Surface Distance (NSD)

Volume metric: N/A

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics have been chosen by following the recommendations set forth in Metrics Reloaded [1]. The following contains the problem-specific answers for semantic segmentation:

Question: Does your data feature consistently small structures relative to pixel size?

Answer: No

Question: Is there exclusive interest in structure centers in your research?

Answer: No

Question: According to the this information, do class confusions, i.e., over- vs. undersegmentation, have equal or unequal weight in your study?

Answer: Equal handling

Question: Are there overlapping or touching target structures in your data?

Answer: No

Question: Is there particular importance of structure boundaries in your research?

Answer: Yes

Question: Is compensation for annotation imprecisions requested in your research?

Answer: Yes

We follow the recommendation of using the following metrics:

Overlap-based metric: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

Boundary-based metric: Normal Surface Distance (NSD)

We have decided not to use any volume metric since this challenge seeks to make methodological comparisons, with no concrete clinical use case in mind.

[1] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nature methods, 21(2):195–212, 2024.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

See Task 1.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For missing metric values for test cases, submissions are evaluated by setting the score to the worst possible value. For DSC and NSD, the worst possible value is 0.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

See Task 1.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

See Task 1.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

See Task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

See Task 1.

TASK 5: Polymicrogyria Classification

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Polymicrogyria is a malformation of cortical development characterized by excessive cortical folding and abnormal cortical layering. It is frequently observed in patients with drug-resistant epilepsy, which remains challenging to characterise due to its heterogeneous radiological presentation. The focus of this task is to evaluate pretrained models on the task of few-shot image-level classification of polymicrogyria. Finetuning and evaluation datasets consist of real-world, clinical data from two different distributions.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

few-shot classification, clinical data

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

See Task 1.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Llucia Coll (llucia.coll.benejam@nru.dk)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

No, but classification labels were provided by clinical personnel.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

See Task 1.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

See Task 1.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

See Task 1.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

See Task 1.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

See Task 1.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

See Task 1.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

See Task 1.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

See Task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

See Task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

See Task 1.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

See Task 1.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

See Task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Pretraining data: See Task 1.

Finetuning data: Ethics approved by the data provider [1].

Test data: approval for data collection and data processing has been granted by the Danish ethics committees and Data Protection Authorities (CVK-2112460).

[1] <https://ruor.uottawa.ca/items/298d789f-e390-43c7-a657-a823701b18b6>

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

See Task 1 for the data usage agreement applicable to all tasks. For finetuning this specific task, the dataset provided in [1] was publicly released under CC-BY-NC-ND [2], which allows redistribution of the material provided that it remains unmodified. Participants will download the unmodified data from that source, and an algorithm for reconstructing the 3D volumes will be provided. [1]

<https://ruor.uottawa.ca/items/298d789f-e390-43c7-a657-a823701b18b6> [2]

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/deed.en>

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

See Task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

See Task 1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Llucia Coll, Alice Schiavone, and Melanie Ganz have access to the validation and test labels for this specific task in the same setting as mentioned in Task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Epilepsy patients of all ages with suspected polymicrogyria.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Finetuning data: Subjects under 18 years of age with a diagnosis of polymicrogyria, as well as a control group, who underwent MRI at the Children's Hospital of Eastern Ontario (Canada).

Validation and test data: Subjects older than 1 year with suspected epilepsy (ICD-10 code G40) who underwent MRI in the Eastern Region of Denmark and whose radiological reports indicated the presence or absence of polymicrogyria.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI scans of the brain, always including T1w images for finetuning, Validation, and Test datasets.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pretrain, Finetune, Validation, and Testing: None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Pretrain: see Task 1. Finetune, Validation, and Testing: None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain MRI scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Patients with epilepsy, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Binary classification of the presence or absence of polymicrogyria on MRI scans, AUROC, Robustness, Few-shot Generalization

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Pretrain dataset: same as Task 1.

Finetune: 3T Siemens Skyra and 1.5T GE Cigna.

Validation and Testing dataset: BrainDrugs WP5: multiple scanners from Siemens, GE, and Philips, including 1.5T and 3T.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

See Task 1.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Pretrain dataset: same as Task 1.

Finetuning dataset: See [1]

Validation and Testing dataset: Data was acquired in routine clinical practice and retrospectively collected from multiple hospitals in the Eastern Region of Denmark, within the BrainDrugs initiative WP5 (<https://braindrugs.nru.dk/>).

[1] <https://ruor.uottawa.ca/items/298d789f-e390-43c7-a657-a823701b18b6>

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Healthcare professionals responsible for performing MRI scans on patients with possible brain-related conditions during regular clinical workflows.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).

- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific MRI visit. For finetuning, Validation, and Test datasets, information always includes T1w, and image-level label indicating the presence or absence of polymicrogyria.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Pretraining cases: same as Task 1. Finetune cases: 92. Validation cases: 37. Test cases: 146.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All data is already annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

See Task 1.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

23 finetuning cases present polymicrogyria, and 69 (3 controls per positive case) are paired healthy controls matched by age and sex. The validation and test cases have equal class distribution.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Validation and test datasets remain unseen to participants.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Pretraining dataset: None.

Finetuning dataset: polymicrogyria search in the PACS [1].

Validation and test datasets: Cases were selected from patients extracted from PACS with an ICD-10 code of G40 (Epilepsy). Pre-selection was performed using a regular expression to identify terms referring to "polymicrogyria." Positive cases were determined through manual annotation of radiological reports by two clinical raters, who provided image-level annotations indicating the presence or absence of polymicrogyria. Cases with disagreement between raters were reviewed and discussed until consensus was reached.

[1] Zhang L, Abdeen N, Lang J. A novel center-based deep contrastive metric learning method for the detection of polymicrogyria in pediatric brain MRI. *Comput Med Imaging Graph.* 2024;114:102373.

doi:10.1016/j.compmedimag.2024.102373

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if

necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Validation and Test cases: Verify the presence or absence of polymicrogyria in radiological reports.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

finetuning cases: a pediatric neuroradiologist with 12 years of experience in reading pediatric brain MRI [1].

Validation and Test cases: a medical doctor and a medical student, supervised by an epilepsy neurologist.

[1] Zhang L, Abdeen N, Lang J. A novel center-based deep contrastive metric learning method for the detection of polymicrogyria in pediatric brain MRI. *Comput Med Imaging Graph.* 2024;114:102373.

doi:10.1016/j.compmedimag.2024.102373

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

finetuning cases: N/A

Validation and Test cases: agreement of two independent raters.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Pretrain data: same as Task 1.

Finetuning data: None.

Validation and Test data: defacing, using pydeface (v 2.0.2)

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Validation and Test data: Labels were derived from the radiological reports, independent of the images.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Multi-class counting metrics: N/A

Per-class counting metric: N/A

Multi-threshold metrics: AUROC (Area Under the Receiver Operator Curve (ROC))

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics have been chosen by following the recommendations set forth in Metrics Reloaded [1]. The following contains the problem-specific answers for Image-level classification:

Question: Which cutoff method on predicted class scores fits your problem more?

Answer: No decision rule applied

Justification: This challenge seeks to make methodological comparisons, with no concrete clinical use case in mind.

Question: Are predicted class probabilities available in your research?

Answer: Yes

Question: Do the provided class prevalences reflect the population of interest in your research?

Answer: No

Question: Is calibration assessment requested in your research?

Answer: No

We follow the recommendation of not including any per-class counting metrics and to evaluate models using AUROC.

[1] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nature methods, 21(2):195–212, 2024.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

See Task 1.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For missing metric values for test cases, submissions are evaluated by setting the score to the worst possible value. For AUROC and F1, the worst possible value is the wrong class prediction with 100% certainty.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

See Task 1.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the

accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

See Task 1.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

See Task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

See Task 1.

TASK 6: Linear Probing

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

In this task, the aim is to directly evaluate the quality of pretraining by measuring the linear separability of the learned embedding space. Participants will submit a single container that produces an embedding per session from the pretrained model. Embeddings will be evaluated on evaluation datasets consisting of two large clinical datasets. The validation dataset is sourced from an undisclosed public dataset. The test dataset is a large private dataset with labels derived from ICD-10 codes and verified by clinical experts. Exact classification targets will remain undisclosed until after the end of the challenge to prevent participants from optimizing their pretraining towards the specific class categories.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

representation probing, embedding evaluation, clinical data

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

See Task 1.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Asbjørn Munk (asmu@di.ku.dk)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Vardan Nersesjan and Christian Krag gave inputs on inclusion and exclusion criteria and clinical relevance of the task.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

See Task 1.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

See Task 1.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

See Task 1.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

See Task 1. Note that no finetuning is allowed.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

See Task 1.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

See Task 1.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

See Task 1.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

See Task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

See Task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

See Task 1. Participants will provide a Docker container that outputs an embedding for each input element. Linear probing will be performed on the embeddings by training 15 linear classifiers with different learning rates for 20 epochs using an 80:20 split of the validation data for choosing the best classifier. Embeddings that are not one-dimensional will be flattened.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

See Task 1.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

See Task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

See Task 1.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

See Task 1.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

See Task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

See Task 1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

See Task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up

- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

18-year-old or older patients diagnosed with undisclosed diagnoses and a control group with no underlying brain conditions, defined as patients with no neurological conditions and not on brain-related medication.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Subjects who underwent an MRI scan and were subsequently diagnosed with neurological and psychiatric diagnoses, and a control group, in multiple hospitals in Denmark (test dataset) and undisclosed countries (train and validation dataset).

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI scans of the brain. The exact sequence types remain undisclosed.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pretrain, Validation, and Testing: None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Pretrain: see Task 1. Validation and Testing: None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain MRI scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Image-based classification of patients with possible undisclosed diagnoses, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Classification of the diagnoses on MRI scans without any finetuning, AUROC, Robustness, Linear separability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Pretrain dataset: same as Task 1. Validation and Test datasets: multiple scanners from GE, Siemens, and Philips.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

See Task 1.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

See Task 1.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Healthcare professionals responsible for performing MRI scans on patients with possible brain-related conditions during regular clinical workflows.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific MRI visit. For Validation and Test datasets, information always includes MRI scans with an undisclosed number of sequences, and an image-level label indicating the diagnosis.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Pretraining cases: same as Task 1. Validation cases: 500. Test cases: 5000.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All data is already annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

See Task 1, except no finetuning is needed.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The balance between cases and controls is chosen according to the real-world distribution. All labels have more than 100 cases in the test set. A case can have multiple values.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Validation data is sourced from an undisclosed public dataset. The test dataset remains unseen to participants.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Pretraining dataset: None. Validation labels selected based on diagnosis codes from the public dataset. Test datasets: Examples were selected based on ICD-10 codes and automatically quality controlled based on Recon-all-clinical [1] estimated dice scores and interquartile range.

[1] Gopinath, Karthik, et al. "Recon-all-clinical": Cortical surface reconstruction and analysis of heterogeneous clinical brain MRI." *Medical Image Analysis* (2025): 103608.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

No manual labeling was performed since labels were derived from ICD-10 codes.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See Task 1. Note that no finetuning dataset is needed.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Labels for the Validation and Test datasets are derived from ICD-10 codes, which may contain errors from misdiagnosis.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Multi-class counting metrics: N/A

Per-class counting metric: OvR F1-score (One vs Rest F1-score)

Multi-threshold metrics: OvR AUROC (One vs Rest Area Under the Receiver Operator Curve (ROC))

Metrics will be macro-averaged with equal class weighting over all class labels.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

"The metrics have been chosen by following the recommendations set forth in Metrics Reloaded [1]. The following contains the problem-specific answers for Image-level classification:

Question: Which cutoff method on predicted class scores fits your problem more?

Answer: Argmax-based

Justification: This challenge seeks to make methodological comparisons, with no concrete clinical use case in mind.

Question: Are predicted class probabilities available in your research?

Answer: Yes

Question: According to this information, are class confusions of unequal severity in your study?

Answer: Yes

Question: Are costs for class confusions available in your research?

Answer: No

Question: Do the provided class prevalences reflect the population of interest in your research?

Answer: Yes

Question: Is calibration assessment requested in your research?

Answer: No

[1] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nature methods, 21(2):195–212, 2024."

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

See Task 1.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For missing metric values for test cases, submissions are evaluated by setting the score to the worst possible value. For AUROC and F1, the worst possible value is 0.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

See Task 1.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

See Task 1.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

See Task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,

- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

See Task 1.

TASK 7: Bias and Fairness

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

This task complements the evaluation of classification performance by measuring group fairness and robustness of pretrained embeddings. Using the same linear probing setup as in Task 6, the container is used to evaluate performance on subgroups. Subgroups are defined based on a set of relevant fairness and robustness factors such as patient demographics. The exact set of patient factors used for evaluation remains undisclosed to avoid targeted de-biasing on a narrow set of evaluated criteria.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

fairness, bias, robustness, clinical data, embedding evaluation

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

See Task 1.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jakob Ambsdorf (jaam@di.ku.dk)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

See Task 6.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

See Task 1.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

See Task 1.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

See Task 1.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

See Task 6.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

See Task 1.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

See Task 1.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

See Task 1.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

See Task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

See Task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

See Task 6.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

See Task 1.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

See Task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

See Task 1.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

See Task 1.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

See Task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

See Task 1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

See Task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training

- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

See Task 6.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Subjects who underwent an MRI scan and were subsequently diagnosed with neurological and psychiatric diagnoses, and a control group, in multiple hospitals in Denmark (test dataset) and undisclosed countries (train and validation dataset).

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI scans of the brain. The exact sequence types remain undisclosed.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pretrain, Validation, and Testing: None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Pretrain: see Task 1. Validation and Testing: None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain MRI scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Image-based classification of patients with possible undisclosed diagnoses, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Group fairness of classification of the diagnoses on MRI scans without any finetuning,AUROC,Fairness,Robustness,Linear seperability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

See Task 6.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

See Task 1.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

See Task 1.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

See Task 6.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

See Task 6.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Pretraining cases: same as Task 1. Validation cases: 500. Test cases: 5000.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All data is already annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

See Task 1, except no finetuning is needed.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

See Task 6.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

See Task 6.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

See Task 6.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

See Task 6.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See Task 1. Note that no finetuning dataset is needed.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

See Task 6.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We define fairness as fairness via maximum group disparity. The maximum disparity between groups is evaluated based on the same metrics as in Task 6:

Multi-class counting metrics: N/A

Per-class counting metric: OvR F1-score (One vs Rest F1-score)

Multi-threshold metrics: OvR AUROC (One vs Rest Area Under the Receiver Operator Curve (ROC))

Metrics will be macro-averaged with equal class weighting over all class labels.

Each metric is calculated over patient groups separated by fairness variables v relating, e.g., to patient demographics such as sex. The maximum disparity D_v of a metric M represents the difference between the highest and lowest performance on groups g_i separated by v . If v is sex, the groups g_i can take values {"male", "female"}. D_v is calculated as:

$$D_v(M) = \max(A_v(M)) - \min(A_v(M))$$

where $A_v(M)$ is the array of macro-averaged metrics on each group g_i .

Finally, the overall fairness score is calculated separately for each of the two metrics M as:

$$\text{Fairness Score}(M) = (1 / |V|) \times \sum_{v \in V} (1 - D_v(M))$$

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

See Task 6 for a justification of using OvR F1-score and OvR AUROC.

We follow the previous MICCAI challenge "MAMA-MIA" (2025) and employ the maximum group disparity as the fairness metric [1]. Maximum group disparity does not measure the utility of models, but complements Task 6 evaluation target by focusing exclusively on group fairness.

[1] L. Garrucho et al. Advancing Generalizability and Fairness in Breast MRI Tumour Segmentation and Treatment Response Prediction (MAMA-MIA). Zenodo, Mar. 19, 2025. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15052678.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

See Task 1.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

See Task 6.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

See Task 1.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the

particular statistical approach.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

See Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

See Task 1.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

See Task 1.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

See Task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

See Task 1.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

References are given in each field.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A